

MANAGING THE CLASSROOM: CLASSROOM MANAGING STRATEGIES, USING THE VOICE, TALKING TO STUDENTS, GIVING INSTRUCTIONS

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Abstract. Education plays the role of a bridge that brings people to the professionalism and helps to realize their goals. Thus, people have to receive education and study hard.

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Introduction. Today we live in the world, where every our step brings us into new path, into new challenge. The XXI century is a century of high innovations and technology development. It is a century where information is exchanged among people globally and where one need to be highly educated in order to survive in very competitive world. People strive to be successful and work hard for building up a better future life conditions. However, for reaching the upper level of life style, mankind has to be well educated. Life is reckoned as the best teacher, as real life situations and conditions provide great experience. However, in order to pass the life school, people have to get prepared. Education plays the role of a bridge that brings people to the professionalism and helps to realize their goals. Thus, people have to receive education and study hard. Schools and other educational facilities are places where people can receive an education from early ages. Parents send their children to school, hoping that it is the best place for their children where they will be able to receive knowledge, and became well educated. However, it is important to consider that schools are places where children from different families, customs and traditions, with different point of views and manners gather together. Teachers need to consider that how to behave, understand and find a common language Considering that the student receives the primary source of knowledge at school, the state authorities pay a great attention to the classroom management all over the world. In order to define the meaning of classroom management, it is important to define what the classroom behavior at schools is, first of all.

Teaching can be both a rewarding and challenging job — and one of the difficulties that arise is classroom management. Effective classroom management is crucial to being able to teach and pass on knowledge to the next generation. If you're a teacher, or thinking of getting a degree in Education, these classroom management strategies can help provide a meaningful learning environment for both teacher and student.

Today, we know more about teaching than we ever have before. Research has shown us that teachers' actions in their classrooms have twice the impact on student achievement as do school policies regarding curriculum, assessment, staff collegiality, and community involvement. We also know that one of the classroom teacher's most important jobs is managing the classroom effectively.

Strategies of Classroom management refers to the wide variety of skills and techniques that teachers use to keep students organized, orderly, focused, attentive, on task, and academically productive during a class. When classroom-management strategies are executed effectively,

teachers minimize the behaviors that impede learning for both individual students and groups of students, while maximizing the behaviors that facilitate or enhance learning. Generally speaking, effective teachers tend to display strong classroom-management skills, while the hallmark of the inexperienced or less effective teacher is a disorderly classroom filled with students who are not working or paying attention.

While a limited or more traditional interpretation of effective classroom management may focus largely on “compliance”—rules and strategies that teachers may use to make sure students are sitting in their seats, following directions, listening attentively, etc.—a more encompassing or updated view of classroom management extends to everything that teachers may do to facilitate or improve student learning, which would include such factors as behavior (a positive attitude, happy facial expressions, encouraging statements, the respectful and fair treatment of students, etc.), environment (for example, a welcoming, well-lit classroom filled with intellectually stimulating learning materials that’s organized to support specific learning activities), expectations (the quality of work that teachers expect students to produce, the ways that teachers expect students to behave toward other students, the agreements that teachers make with students), materials (the types of texts, equipment, and other learning resources that teachers use), or activities (the kinds of learning experiences that teachers design to engage student interests, passions, and intellectual curiosity). Given that poorly designed lessons, uninteresting learning materials, or unclear expectations, for example, could contribute to greater student disinterest, increased behavioral problems, or unruly and disorganized classes, classroom management cannot be easily separated from all the other decisions that teachers make. In this more encompassing view of classroom management, good teaching and good classroom management become, to some degree, indistinguishable.

In practice, classroom-management techniques may appear deceptively simple, but successfully and seamlessly integrating them into the instruction of students typically requires a variety of sophisticated techniques and a significant amount of skill and experience. While the specific techniques used to manage classrooms and facilitate learning can vary widely in terminology, purpose, and execution, the following representative examples

1.1. Classroom management is a term used by teachers to describe the process of ensuring that classroom lessons run smoothly despite disruptive behavior by students. The term also implies the prevention of disruptive behavior. It is possibly the most difficult aspect of teaching for many teachers; indeed experiencing problems in this area causes some to leave teaching altogether. In the US National Educational Association reported that 36% of teachers said they would probably not go into teaching if they had to decide again. A major reason was “negative student attitudes and discipline”.

According to Moskowitz & Hayman (1999), once a teacher loses control of their classroom, it becomes increasingly more difficult for them to regain that control. Also, research from Berliner (1999) and Brophy & Good (1998) shows that the time a teacher has to take to correct misbehavior caused by poor classroom management skills results in a lower rate of academic engagement in the classroom. From the student’s perspective, effective classroom management involves clear communication of behavioral and academic expectations as well as a cooperative learning environment. Douglas Brooks (1998) reports seminal research on the first day of school activity selection and sequence of novice middle school teachers compared with experienced, successful classroom managers. Brooks reports that effective classroom managers organized their activities on the first day of school consistent with the emerging needs of the

students. These middle school student needs were the following: 1. Am I welcome? 2. What are we going to do today? 3. Am I in the right room? 4. Is the teacher interested in me? 5. What are the rules for this classroom? 6. What are the goals, instructional methods and assessment systems for the class? 7. Is the teacher interested in how I learn best? 8. What interests does the teacher have that I can relate to? 9. What are we expected to do for tomorrow? And finally 10. Will the teacher answer a question I have after class? In response to these emerging and sequential student needs effective middle school teachers organize the first day activities in the following sequence: 1. Personally greet students 2. Advance organizer for the session at the bell, 3. Roll and Seating 4. Student Information cards 5. Introduce 5 core rules (entry, listening, raising hands, leaving other's stuff alone and finally exiting the class) 6. Describe class goals, instructional methods and grading system, 7. Assess preferred learning styles, 8. Self-disclosure 9. Preview of next session and finally 10 Access after class. Middle school teachers that meet these 10 student needs with specific activities tend to communicate competence and effectively communicate behavioral and academic expectations.

Classroom management is closely linked to issues of motivation, discipline and respect. Methodologies remain a matter of passionate debate amongst teachers; approaches vary depending on the beliefs a teacher holds regarding educational psychology. A large part of traditional classroom management involves behavior modification, although many teachers see using behavioral approaches alone as overly simplistic. Many teachers establish rules and procedures at the beginning of the school year. According to Goodman (2008), rules give students concrete direction to ensure that our expectation becomes a reality.

They also try to be consistent in enforcing these rules and procedures. Many would also argue for positive consequences when rules are followed, and negative consequences when rules are broken. There are newer perspectives on classroom management that attempt to be holistic. One example is affirmation teaching, which attempts to guide students toward success by helping them see how their effort pays off in the classroom. It relies upon creating an environment where students are successful as a result of their own efforts. By creating this type of environment, students are much more likely to want to do well. Ideally, this transforms a classroom into a community of well-behaved and self-directed learners.

In recent years, classroom management has received an increasing amount of attention from education leaders, reformers, and researchers, who have begun to investigate, analyze, and document the effective strategies used by successful teachers. The growing emphasis on classroom management is based on the general recognition that effective instruction requires effective classroom management, and that strong management skills are the foundation of strong teaching. In addition, there are now more professional — development opportunities related to classroom management being offered to teachers, and there have been discussions about the role of practical teaching techniques in teacher education and certification programs, and about whether such programs have overemphasized education theory at the expense of practical, applied skills that teachers will need in the classroom, such as classroom-management strategies.

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